

INNOVATIVE FORMS AND METHODS - AS A FACTOR OF SUCCESSFUL IMPROVEMENT OF TEACHERS' COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE

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Abstract: in modern conditions of reforming education, the status of a teacher, his educational functions are radically changing, the requirements for his professional and pedagogical competence, for the level of his professionalism, change accordingly.

Key words: professional competence, methods of education and training, advanced training of teachers, modeling, training.

One of the indicators of the communicative competence of the educator is his ability to self-improve, which is expressed in dissatisfaction, awareness of the imperfection of the current state of the educational process and the desire for growth and self-education.

Today teacher:

- a harmoniously developed, internally rich personality striving for spiritual, professional, general cultural and physical improvement;
- knows how to choose the most effective methods of education and training, means and technologies for the implementation of the tasks;
- knows how to organize the activities of preschool children;
- the educator has a high level of professional competence, must constantly improve their knowledge and skills, improve their skills and have diverse interests.

Improving the quality of preschool education directly depends on the professional level of the teaching staff.

Therefore, we believe that the task of a methodologist in a preschool institution is to develop a system with which it will be possible to use new effective methods and techniques to improve the skills of teachers.

In this regard, we believe that it is necessary to involve teachers in pedagogical and cognitive activities, using active teaching methods and techniques that should be used:

One of the forms of increasing the professional competence of teachers is the pedagogical council, which is a collegial governing body of the institution, where issues of the content of education, management and organization of the educational process are resolved. To stimulate the creative thinking of teachers, awaken their need for a business conversation and influence the situation in the institution, we propose to use unusual, modern and intensified forms of behavior: "teachers council-seminar", "teachers council - presentation", "scientific-practical conference", etc. [2].

Seminar - creative classes are aimed at developing creative thinking and creating innovative projects [2].

Seminar - press conferences help to quickly find information on individual problems, to comprehend it deeply, to discuss individual issues with colleagues [5]. Game modeling. Business and role-playing games imply the simulation of a real process, during which optimal professional decisions are made based on the analysis of artificially created pedagogical situations. A business game as a teaching method allows you to "live" this or that practical situation. In the course of it, you can solve problems of varying complexity. It activates the creative initiative of educators, ensures a high level of assimilation of theoretical knowledge and the development of professional skills [5].

Training is a system of specially selected exercises for self-regulation of the psycho-physiological state, training of various mental qualities of a person (attention, memory, will, etc.), working out methods for receiving and processing information, mastering various methods of organizing work. The great value of this

kind of exercise is in the opportunity to get an assessment of your behavior from the outside, to make a self-assessment and an assessment of your actions. Training more than other forms (methods) creates a situation of mandatory "immersion" in oneself and one's activity. Training is a form of work aimed at developing certain professional skills and abilities. Training can be used both as an independent form of methodical work, and as a methodical technique during a seminar [5].

A quiz is an entertaining game during which, in a certain sequence (logical, chronological, etc.), participants are asked questions to which they give answers orally or in writing. The quiz allows you to expand and deepen the knowledge gained as a result of self-education and practical activities, improve the skills of analyzing and systematizing informatization from various sources, modeling and predicting actions aimed at creative changes in pedagogical practice [5].

Master Class. Its main goal is to get acquainted with the pedagogical experience, the system of work, the author's findings and everything that helped the teacher to achieve the best results. The master class can be held both inside the preschool educational institution and for teachers of the preschool district, city and region [2].

Creative groups are a form of methodical work with teachers of a preschool educational institution. It involves the implementation of such an approach to the implementation of methodological work in an educational institution, which allows you to involve teachers in experimental and research activities [1].

The round table is one of the forms of communication between teachers. When discussing any issues of upbringing and education of preschoolers, circular pedagogical forms of placement of participants make it possible to make the team self-governing, allows you to put all participants in an equal position, ensures interaction and openness. The role of the organizer of the "round table" is to think over and prepare questions for discussion aimed at achieving a specific goal [2].

Self-education is the independent acquisition of knowledge from various sources, taking into account the interests and inclinations of each particular teacher. As a process of mastering knowledge, it is closely related to self-education and is considered its integral part [3].

In the process of self-education, a person develops the ability to independently organize their activities to acquire new knowledge.

A creative report is a form that provides a report on the work of a methodological formation or a specific teacher. The purpose of such a report is to systematize the process of accumulation and generalization of pedagogical experience within the educational institution. As a result of the report, the methodological formation or the educator present the accumulated methodological, didactic, visual materials, introduce them to their pedagogical achievements, approaches to solving pedagogical problems, and the formed style of work. The report can take the form of a presentation, an exhibition, an invitation to a creative laboratory [4].

The Brainstorming or Brainstorming method is a group creative thinking procedure, more precisely, it is a means of obtaining a large number of ideas from a group of people in a short period of time [4].

This method can be actively used at meetings of the creative group to discuss the plan or conduct various events: children's vacations, competitions, pedagogical competitions, methodological associations, etc.

Having gone through all forms of methodical work organized in a certain system, teachers not only improve their professional level, it becomes a need for them to learn something new, to develop their own style of everyday pedagogical activity.

Improving the quality of preschool education is directly dependent on the professional level of teaching staff.

The professionalism of a teacher working with children is associated, first of all, with communicative competence, with the ability to play and communicate with

children. That is why special attention should be focused on improving this competence of teachers. To this end, various forms and methods are widely used in working with teachers.

But at the same time, it should be noted that no forms of work by themselves, regardless of the content of advanced training of a teacher, can guarantee a creative approach. There is not and cannot be a division of forms into new and old, modern and non-modern, since each of them corresponds to a certain content. Any traditional form can be active if it is built correctly in terms of content and methods and implements such important functions as informational, orienting and developing. It should be noted that group activities create favorable conditions for learning and cooperation of teachers, cooperating with more qualified colleagues, “less creative” teachers begin to work more successfully.

Improving the quality of preschool education is directly dependent on staff. It is important to note that in the modern conditions of reforming education, the status of a teacher, his educational functions are radically changing, and the requirements for his professional and pedagogical competence, for the level of his professionalism, change accordingly. At the moment, we note that today there is a demand for a teacher who is creative, competent, capable of developing skills to mobilize his personal potential in the modern system of education and development of a preschooler.

Summing up, we can say that a well-constructed system of innovative forms of work with teaching staff will lead to an increase in the level of educational work of preschool educational institutions and will unite the team of teachers.

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